

ELEMENTS OF THE MANAGEMENT SYSTEM OF INDUSTRIAL SAFETY, LABOR PROTECTION AND ENVIRONMENTAL PROTECTION AT THE "UZBEKISTAN GTL" PLANT

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Abstract: We can include the following in the main principles of security policy. The head of this department is responsible for the organization of industrial safety (IS), labor protection (MM) and environmental protection (AMM) at the plant. Contracting organizations are selected on the basis of a tender for the organization of work on improving the quality of work, carrying out attestation and passporting of workplaces, identification of assets.

Key words and phrases: Risk, risk, resources, Risk quantification, risk, quantitative assessment, engineering method, modeling, expert, social survey.

Introduction. The ultimate goal of all reforms in the economic and political spheres implemented in our country is to create decent living conditions for all citizens living in our country. Of course, at present, the creation of decent living conditions in any society is carried out on the basis of scientific and technical progress, and this, along with the relief of human labor, creates various dangerous factors that result in various forms of harmful factors, harmful factors, injuries, injuries and occupational diseases occur. It is for this reason that a person is constantly active. Therefore, it is necessary to study the dangerous and harmful factors that occur during production processes in industrial enterprises, depending on the type of work and working conditions, and implement a plan of

measures.[1] In any production process, there is no such thing as an absolutely safe system, therefore, the study of the "elements of industrial safety, labor protection and environmental protection management system at the UZBEKISTAN GTL" plant and the causes of their prevention if used, it gives its effectiveness in both production and non-production processes.[6]

The main part: Paying attention to the fact that the life and health of workers and the preservation of environmental cleanliness are always the priority in relation to the final results of any activities or production of an economic, technological or other nature.

The strategic goal of the plant in terms of industrial and environmental safety, labor protection and civil protection should be one of the primary tasks and it must be confirmed with concrete results.

Industrial and environmental safety, labor protection and civil protection is the most important element of production, the systematic management process of which is considered as an element of production management and the negative impact on the life and health of workers, work equipment and the environment. management of professional risk aimed at elimination.

From the general director of the plant to the shop, department heads and foremen, they must strictly adhere to this safety policy, providing practical and methodological support to specialists.

Relevance of the topic: Organization of security and provision of resources. The head of this department is responsible for the organization of industrial safety (IS), labor protection (MM) and environmental protection (AMM) at the plant. The organization and control of the use of material resources aimed at ensuring safety is defined as the direct task of the heads of the workshop and facilities.[2]

Management of contractors and suppliers. For the training of workers on industrial safety and labor protection, professional development, attestation and

passporting of workplaces, and organization of work on identification of goods, contracting organizations are selected on the basis of a tender and their activities comply with the requirements of industrial safety, the safety management system. , the orientation of the proposed service to eliminate risks, the qualification and competence of its employees, the existence of special training programs, and experience in this field are taken into account. Supervision of the contractors' compliance with the requirements of industrial safety and labor protection and the terms of the contract is assigned to the workshops and departments where this work is performed. [2]

Risk management. Since risk is a complex and multi-characteristic concept, its taxonomy, nomenclature, quantification and identification play an important role in ensuring industrial safety and labor protection, as well as in a deeper study of the nature of risk.

Rationale of the topic: Quantification of risk. Quantification means giving numerical characteristics to complex concepts whose quality level is determined and evaluated.

Numerical, point and other methods of quantification are used. The most common quantitative risk assessment criterion is risk ("risk"), risk taking, that is, going against the risk.

Quantitative assessment is the ratio of the expected negative consequences during the activity in a certain period to the possible risk and negative consequences. When determining the risk, the class of consequences should be indicated.

As mentioned above, "Risk" is the frequency of risk occurrence and realization, that is, it is a quantitative risk assessment criterion.

Risk is the opposite of risk.

Risk is the frequency of occurrence of risk, that is, the criterion of quantitative assessment of risk.

Quantitative assessment is the ratio of the probability of occurrence of

undesirable consequences occurring in a certain interval of the activity period to the risk and consequence.

where n is the number of workers killed in production in one year;

$$R_{ur} = \frac{n}{N};$$

N is the total number of employees.

Risk is divided into personal and social types depending on the type of risk. Personal risk characterizes the risk directed at one person, and social (more precisely, group) risk characterizes the risk affecting a group of people [40].

Many experts suggest using the financial dimension of human life when comparing the risk during activity, i.e. risk-taking and the work (profit) performed as a result of activity. Of course, this proposal is not supported by all experts. But if the question is "How much money should be spent to save a human life?" this proposal is considered correct. According to the results of the research of some foreign scientists, the safety of human life is 7 million out of 650 thousand. It can be valued up to USD.[3]

The procedure for determining the risk is considered very approximate, and it can be divided into four different methods:

engineering style. This method is based on static data, risk frequency calculation, probabilistic safety analysis, risk tree construction;

model. In this method, a model of dangerous and harmful factors affecting an individual, a group of people, etc. is created;

expert, that is, the probability of the occurrence of various events is determined based on the judgment and opinion of experienced specialists (experts).

social survey. In this case, the probability of occurrence of events is determined by knowing the opinion of the population.

The above methods show different aspects of risk. Therefore, in

practice, it is advisable to use these methods in a complex manner.

Traditional safety techniques require a strict requirement, that is, that every production process should be without a single accident, damage, or injury. But life shows that this concept is inadequate to the laws of the technosphere. For this reason, current laws of safety abandon the concept of absolute safety and promote the concept of acceptable risk.

The concept of acceptable risk includes technical, economic, social and political aspects and is a compromise between the level of safety during the activity and the possibility of achieving safety.

The economic opportunities for improving the security of technical systems may be unlimited, but spending too much money on security can lead to harm in the social sphere, that is, for example, medical care may deteriorate. This means that as the cost increases, the technical risk decreases and the social risk increases.

In some countries, the permissible level of risk is determined by law. This amount can be from 10^{-8} to 10^{-6} . In general, the maximum permissible level of risk for the ecosystem envisages the injury of 5% of the type of biogenesis in the system. Currently, the acceptable, i.e. permissible, level of risk has not been accepted in our country. However, this concept is criticized and denied by some experts. However, the actual level of risk is 2-3 times higher than the permissible level of risk. Therefore, implementing an acceptable concept of risk in life is one of the measures aimed at protecting a person from danger.

One of the main tasks of industrial safety is to increase the level of safety as much as possible. This task can be carried out through activities in the following three directions:[1]

1. Improvement of technical systems and objects.
2. Training of highly qualified specialists and personnel.
3. Elimination of emergency situations.

In accordance with the above, we can also divide the methods of risk

management into 4 groups: technical, organizational, administrative and economic. If improvement of technical systems and objects is carried out by technical means, training of personnel and elimination of emergency situations is carried out by organizational and administrative methods, economic means of insurance, payment of monetary "compensation" (contribution) for damage, dangerous conditions various payments are made through activities such as giving. Therefore, the basis of risk management is the comparison of the benefit obtained at the expense of risk reduction as a result of additional spending, that is, the amount of increase in the level of safety.

Risk management requires first of all risk study and logical analysis. Probable risk is studied based on a certain sequence and is displayed according to this sequence.

Step 1 – Initial risk analysis.

- a) identification of sources of danger;
- b) identify elements of the system that cause this risk;
- v) to establish certain limits in the analysis, that is, to separate the risks that cannot be studied.

Step 2 - Determining the sequence of occurrence of risks, building a "tree of events and risks".

Step 3. Consequence analysis.

Stages 1 and 2 of the above-mentioned sequence of risk studies are carried out before the event (consequence) occurs, that is, before the start of the activity process, and serve to ensure safety, and from stage 3, it is necessary to ensure safety in the future. used to develop activities.

Stages 1 and 2 of the sequence of risk studies presented above are carried out before the event (consequence), that is, before the start of the activity process, and serve to ensure safety. The 3rd stage will be used to develop measures to ensure safety and reduce the number of accidents in the future.

Determining the procedure for assessing and minimizing risks that may occur in production provides an opportunity to obtain information on reducing the impact of this risk on the life and health and safety of workers, and realizes the following goals:

- identify the source of risks and develop measures to eliminate them;
- determining the level of risk;
- determining measures aimed at reducing the level of risk or eliminating it.

Risk assessment is carried out according to the approved methodology M-16.02.01-01. [3]

Conclusion: Risk reduction or elimination is achieved through the implementation of management programs aimed at the implementation and monitoring of goals and tasks. The management program consists of a plan for the implementation of activities, which will consist of coordination and control of responsible and controlling persons, activities and resources in order to achieve the set goals for industrial safety and labor protection within the specified time. Accident and accident prevention measures are a priority in this management program.

Temporary change management includes the areas of organizational structure, workforce, systems, processes, equipment, products, materials and substances, legislation and regulatory framework.

All changes must be clearly defined and communicated to the appropriate personnel prior to change management. Monitoring and control are required at various stages of the change management cycle. It is recommended to use order-permits when required in the complex of change management processes. The type of permits is determined depending on the process to be performed and the type of risk that occurs.

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